

Title: IOT Solutions

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INTRODUCTION:

The Internet of things (IoT) is the network of physical devices, vehicles, home appliances and other items embedded with electronics, software, sensors, actuators, and network connectivity which enables these objects to connect and exchange data.[1][2][3] Each thing is uniquely identifiable through its embedded computing system but is able to inter-operate within the existing Internet infrastructure.

Experts estimate that the IoT will consist of about 30 billion objects by 2020.[4] It is also estimated that the global market value of IoT will reach \$7.1 trillion by 2020. .

AIM:

The Internet of Things (IoT) is aimed at enabling the interconnection and integration of the physical world and the cyber space.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

IOTA is a revolutionary new, next generation public distributed ledger that utilizes a novel invention, called a "Tangle", at its core. The Tangle is a new data structure based on a Directed Acyclic Graph. As such it has no Blocks, no Chain and also no Miners. Because of this radical new architecture, things in IOTA work quite differently compared to other Blockchains.

RESULTS:

IOTA has 4 HUGE advantages over Blockchain cryptocurrencies

- Scalable
- Decentralized
- Modular
- Fee Less

CONCLUSIONS:

According to the results of this study, As much as Network will grow for IOTA, transaction would be more faster and cost less as its based on Tangle.

KEYWORDS:

IOT; IOTA; Tangle, Blockchain.

BIOGRAPHY:

Kulwant Singh has completed his M.Sc- IT at the age of 27 years from AAIDU Allahabad and Bachelor from Punjabi University, Patiala , INDIA. He is the director of Percept Software Systems Pvt Ltd., a premier IT service organization. He got following international certification based on his skillset

- SCJP- Sun Certified Java Professional
- MCSE- Microsoft Certified Professional
- MCP- Microsoft Certified Professional (Dotnet 2.0)
- OCA- Oracle Certified Associate.